

***Magonote* – Making Complex Home Electronics Accessible by Empowering the Family Technology Lead**

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Abstract

Advances in technology continually increase the ability, but also the complexity, of consumer electronics. While manufacturers try to remedy this by designing programmable remote controls or consolidating multiple interfaces into one, our research shows that families often rely upon a single person – the family “technology lead” – to operate their home electronics for them. Instead of trying to create simpler interfaces for complex home electronics that can be used by all, we believe that a system which empowers the family technology lead will not only facilitate the operation of complex home electronics, but will bring families closer together. In this paper we present *Magonote*, a conceptual system created using iterative, user-centered design methodologies, as a solution to this problem.

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Introduction

Advances in technology continually increase the ability, but also the complexity, of consumer electronics. This is especially true when several devices must be configured to work together, such as a digital TV digital video recorder, satellite set-top box, DVD player, and surround sound system. Manufacturers of consumer electronics attempt to remedy this by designing programmable remote controls or interfaces that consolidate multiple, complex user interfaces into one. They then attempt to make this remote control or consolidated interface “easy” so that everyone in a household can use these installations. Unfortunately, the consumer electronics industry has not had great success in making these complex systems accessible and configurable by all.

However, these efforts overlook a subtle social dynamic that occurs within families. When faced with using complex home electronics, families cope by creating hand written instructions (Figure 1) in order to teach each other how to use the devices. In Japan, where our research was conducted, user-centered research methods were used to show that a single person – the family “technology lead” – is the one who creates this kind of assistance. This single person (he or she may be a father, mother, son or daughter) – is responsible for managing the family’s home electronics and takes great pride in being able to operate these devices for the rest of their family members, even those who do not live under the same roof.

Figure 1: Example of hand-written instructions created by one family’s “technology lead” for the rest of the family.

Based on this finding, we propose a radically new design that takes advantage of this family dynamic. The proposed system, called *Magonote*, meaning “Grandchild’s helping hand” in Japanese – otherwise known as a back-scratcher – creates the opportunity for family members to

depend upon and assist one another. It allows the family technology lead to remotely operate the interface of home electronics that are connected to the family's DLNA (Digital Living Network Alliance) network. Using a device such as a cell phone or PC, the technology lead remotely logs on to a family member's TV or recording device, and operates the system for them by way of macros. Macros can be transferred and replayed, enabling the technology lead to support his or her family even when they are not physically present. Users in Japan have shown great interest in this system's ability to provide remote technological support to other family members.

Related Work

To address complexity in home electronics, researchers and manufacturers have created a variety of devices, such as programmable universal remote controls. A commercial example of a programmable remote control is the Harmony series from Logitech. It has a simple, task-based interface that allows the user to select such options as "play movie in VCR" or "play DVD." However, the built-in set of tasks is limited to the ones that the company has pre-programmed, and adding support for new tasks is time consuming. (Nichols *et al.*, 2006) Other examples include the Philips Pronto. This programmable remote control enables users to design screens and assign complex functions to a single on-screen button, but it also requires a dedicated time commitment to program.

An alternative approach to simplifying home electronics is to make them interoperable. Just as many computer products are UPnP (universal plug-and-play) compatible, different manufacturer's home electronics are also becoming UPnP compatible. This protocol is being promoted by the Digital Living Network Alliance (DLNA), and in Japan, digital TVs, cable boxes, stereo systems and even digital cameras are increasingly becoming DLNA-certified. This means that a central device, such as a digital video recorder, can act as a server while all other connected devices act as clients. Another similar standard core specification is Home Audio Video Interoperability (HAVi) which uses the IEEE 1394 protocol to connect home electronic devices. The benefit of all of these systems is that a single interface can be used to operate the connected devices.

A more advanced example of simplifying interfaces is the *personal universal controller* (PUC). The PUC engages in two-way communication with everyday appliances by first downloading the appliances' functions to a hand-held device such as a smart phone or PDA, and then automatically creating an interface for controlling the appliance on the hand-held device. (Nichols *et al.*, 2002) The benefit to this system is that it creates consistency between devices

such as a TV and digital video recorder, and provides a way to operate all of these devices from a hand-held interface, much like a programmable remote control.

While all of these ideas are technologically sound, they are problematic because they are designed to *replace* the family technology lead. In other words, their purpose is to consolidate multiple user interfaces into a single interface that is theoretically easy enough to use by all so that they do not have to rely upon someone else to instruct them in the use of their home electronic products. While this may seem to be desirable, it fails to recognize the family “technology lead” as an important entity that operates their home electronics for other family members. In order to empower the family technology lead, they need to be given the opportunity to help other family members in an efficient, timely manner. This is an important aspect of any technological support solution designed for the home. Research on smart homes shows that the ideal level of automation is one that partially automates the parent’s tasks. Dressing small children and cooking meals is stressful, but also necessary for the parent to feel like an ideal parent (Lee *et al.*, 2006). To create more time for parents and enhance the qualities of parenting activities as a result, a smart home could assist with mundane tasks and provide a “gift of time.” Likewise, a system that simplifies complex home electronics should enable the family technology lead to dedicate more time to assisting other family members.

In order to understand how such a system can strengthen families’ ties, we must first understand the ecological constructs of a product such as a TV. The product ecology is a means for understanding how the use of a TV by the father, mother, or children of a family is interconnected, yet provides a different experience for each one (Forlizzi, 2008). For instance, the mother may be more interested in what is broadcasted on the TV, and the father may be more interested in the TV’s functions. Furthermore, the presence of the TV may affect how the family interacts with all of their home entertainment products. The purchase of a new TV may mean that the old TV is given to the children, or that the same model is purchased for an elderly parent as well. Clearly, the way in which each member of a family interacts with a product is different, and yet, the interface is designed with the intent of having each member of the family interact with it in the same manner. This discrepancy gives rise to roles in the family, namely the role of technology lead, the person who learns and operates the interface, and the technology followers, the remaining members of the family who rely upon the technology lead to enable them to enjoy the broadcasted contents of the TV. We have already established that the followers in the family do not want to learn how to use the product. Attempting to teach them how to use the product will only serve to disrupt the balance of this product ecology. The balance in the family is maintained by allowing the technology lead to fulfil their role as the one

who performs functions for the rest of the family members. Hence, *Magonote* can serve to maintain this balance by empowering the family technology lead so that they can perform their duties as technology lead in a timely, flexible and visible manner.

Design Process and Findings

The project, part of a one-year master's thesis project in interaction design at Carnegie Mellon University, began with the intention of creating an intuitive interface that would eliminate the need for instruction manuals once and forever. To this end, the following methods were selected in order to understand how family members teach each other how to use their home electronics. As research progressed, however, it soon became apparent that families functioned quite successfully by ignoring difficult interfaces all together and relying upon the human support of the family technology lead.

Contextual Interviews

Two-hour long interviews were conducted with eight families (n = 21, age 16-65) to determine how they transfer knowledge and what they like and dislike about current interfaces and functions. During these interview sessions, it quickly became clear that for all families, one person was in charge of the family's home electronics. This person was identified as the "technology lead" and all other members of the family were identified as "technology followers," and the difference in their responses to the questions was noted. At the end of the interview session, the technology lead was asked to show the technology follower how to perform a certain function appropriate to the electronics that they owned.

Diaries

Eighteen family members were asked to keep a week-long diary of their viewing, learning and teaching habits. The diaries contained questions designed to give a more detailed account of how they learn from each other (if at all), and how they use their home electronics on a daily basis. Upon reviewing the results, differences in responses between the groups were noted.

Draw the Experience

After the diaries were submitted, seven of the technology leads from the eight families were individually interviewed again. As they reflected upon what they learned about their viewing,

learning and teaching habits, they were asked to draw their vision of the ideal remote control. (Figure 2) One participant drew a remote control that was a blueprint of his family apartment from which he could control all of his family’s electronic devices. Another participant drew a picture of a cell phone by which she could control multiple devices belonging to all family members. Another interesting variation was a remote control that contained buttons for each member of the family, but that were to be used by the technology lead in order to manage the viewing preferences of each family member, not by the family members themselves.

Figure 2: Sketches of ideal remote controls. From left to right: a “blueprint” remote control, a cell phone remote control and a remote control limiting functions for each family member.

Our research revealed that, despite varying levels of ability, all families clearly consisted of one technology lead, and several technology followers.

Common Characteristics of the Technology Lead

Based upon interview and diary responses, family technology leads displayed the following common characteristics about tech leads:

- Are “let me drive” type users, meaning that they don’t want anyone to tell them how to do something. They want to learn on their own by going on-line or reading reference books.
- Have strong opinions (both positive and negative) about technology and are more likely to call customer services when problems arise.
- Are eager for technological change.
- Feel obligated to support other family members, even when they are busy and even if the extended family member lives apart from them.

- Are often the ones who purchased the home electronic devices. They have a financial interest in making the products work.

Characteristics of the Technology Followers

Technology followers showed the following common characteristics:

- Are “do it for me” or “show me how” type users, and are quick to ask the technology lead, rather than read the instructions, when they have a question about using a product.
- Do not go on-line or call the customer service center.
- Rely upon people around them to answer questions about matters in general, not just technological questions.

Family Dynamics

When asked to demonstrate how they instruct other family members how to use their home electronics, we discovered that the technology lead does not actually “teach” the followers how to operate the devices. Of the seven technology leads that gave a demonstration of how they teach, such as how to delete a recorded program, five technology leads taught the technology followers either by showing them or by doing it for them. Only two of the technology leads let the technology follower try an operation for him or herself. Of these two technology followers who did the task themselves, only one appeared to want to figure out the task on their own. It was clear that the family technology lead needed to assert their role as the single person in charge of the family’s home electronics. In one family, the mother was the technology lead, even though the father was more knowledgeable about technology in general. In another case, a daughter assumed the role of technology lead the moment she turned 16 years old, taking the role from her father. And in another case, the son was the technology lead for the two TVs and VCR owned by his elderly parents, even though he had only one TV at home. This is significant in that it shows how each family maintained the fabric of their relationship by recognizing and respecting the family technology lead, even though the technology lead might not have been the most knowledgeable about technology in general.

Design Implications

We believe that these findings have important implications for the design of home electronics. The current thinking of user interface design is that it should be simple enough for everyone to use. Using an automobile as a metaphor, we might say that the current thinking of user interface

design is that “everyone has to drive.” (Figure 3) In other words, all users have to equally learn how to navigate and use the product’s interface. This requires manufacturers to spend a great deal of time and money trying to make user interfaces as simple as possible. However, our research shows that the only person truly interested in learning the interface is the family technology lead. Rather than creating a system that tries to help the followers explain the problem and raise their level of understanding, research suggests that, a solution that enables technology followers to ask a question quickly and have the technology lead resolve the question quickly is better. (Figure 4) Note that this proposed system does not intend to replace the user interfaces of home electronics, but is designed to work in conjunction with current interfaces.

Figure 3: The current thinking is to design a single interface for all levels of user.

Figure 4: We propose designing a system for the family technology lead so that they can support all other members of the family.

Concept generation and needs validation

Twenty-eight storyboards were created based upon the concept of designing for the family technology lead. The scenarios and the underlying needs they intended to address were evaluated using a needs validation methodology known as “Speed Dating” (Davidoff *et al.*, 2007) with seven technology leads, male and female (age 30-50). The storyboards focused on ways by which the technology lead might offer support in situations where remote assistance is required. Based upon the reaction to these storyboards, the concept was further refined using three specific scenarios that encompassed all of the functions deemed necessary for the

Magonote system. The aim was to discover what emotional elements and technological features would make the technology lead feel empowered. We found that in order for the family technology lead to feel like they are performing their job, they would not only have to be able to control the home electronic devices of other family members, but they would have to be able to do it in a way that was visible, repeatable and transferable.

Final Design

Our final design for *Magonote* empowers the family technology lead by allowing a single family member to remotely operate the interface of home electronics using a device such as a smart phone or PDA. (Figure 5) This is accomplished by using DLNA (Digital Living Network Alliance) compliant devices connected to the family VPN (virtual private network). Upon accessing the user interface of a connected device, the technology lead operates the followers' device as necessary. For instance, they might set the followers' digital video recorder to record a TV program. These actions are saved as a macro that is then sent from the lead to the follower's home. The macro can be set to run automatically, or it can be run at will by the follower. The use of a macro is important in that it enables the technology lead's support to be transferable, visible and repeatable by all family members.

Figure 5: Using a PDA or smart phone, the family technology lead makes changes to the followers' home electronics remotely and then sends those changes to the follower as a macro.

Visual Design

The system had to be simple enough to be used by technology leads that are willing to operate, but not necessarily knowledgeable about, complex home electronics. We needed to show that the application is meant to be a bridge between people, rather than a high-tech gimmick. Furthermore, we also needed to show that the application has limitations and is not capable of complex troubleshooting tasks.

To resolving these issues, we conducted a series of paper prototype tests with five technology leads. A different lead was used for each test, so they all saw the interface for the first time during the test. The end result was an interface flow that was simple and intuitive enough to be used by all levels of technology lead.

In order to convey the feeling that the system is a bridge between people, as well as show that the system is not able to control all aspects of a family's home electronics, a home motif using "yarn" and "buttons" was selected. (Figure 6)

Figure 6: A knitted background and buttons are used to convey a sense of home and ease of use.

Among other background texture options, the "knitted" design that best reflected the systems' ability to weave together the operations of his or her home electronics for the rest of the family members, and "knitting" together the fabric of the family.

Strengthen a family's ties by maintaining roles

This system is still in development, but our research indicates that it can be very successful at maintaining family ties by maintaining roles. Currently, the family technology lead is relied upon to do a variety of tasks such as troubleshoot problems with the TV, make recordings for other family members and do maintenance work (such as deleting programs). The role of the family technology lead breaks down when they are not present at home because they are at work, or because one of their followers lives far away. *Magonote* can empower the family technology lead by enabling the family technology lead to offer the support that they normally provide at home, even when they are not present.

Our fieldwork also revealed another unexpected benefit. In addition to support, the family technology lead can also provide support through creative applications of the system, such as creating a gift recording. While the concept of remote support received a highly positive reaction from our test subjects, it was the scenario where a son sets an elder parent's video recorder to make a secret gift recording that was most appreciated.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have illustrated a concept for a programmable remote control device that can be used to empower the family technology lead and thereby maintain their role within the family as the one who manages their family's home electronics. Various manufacturers have already developed programmable remote control devices with the intention of simplifying complex home electronics, but in addition to being difficult to program, these devices ignore the fact that most users are not interested in learning the details of how to operate their home electronics. Our research using user-centered design methods shows that most users rely upon a single, family technology lead to operate and manage their home electronics. The presence of this technology lead is not only one of convenience, but plays an important part in knitting together the fabric of the family. This role is especially important when family members are not living under the same roof. Our proposal is to empower this family technology lead by enabling the technology lead to maintain their role even when they are not at home or when they have to support someone living at a distance. Using needs validation methodologies, we have designed a system that does just this. *Magonote* empowers the family technology lead by enabling them to remotely operate the home electronics of family members by creating and sending macros over a virtual private network. The next step is to address the technical issues of creating macros for home electronics

and create a working prototype. Using this prototype, we hope to be able to evaluate the emotional impact that the *Magonote* system has on maintaining family ties.

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